

A Tool-based Process for Generating Attention Distribution Predictions

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Monitoring is one of the most important tasks for an operator driving a vehicle. Designing Human Machine Interfaces (HMI) for vehicles requires optimizing what is presented to the most limited resource: the driver's visual attention. But how a car driver divides attention is hard to anticipate for a human factors (HF) expert. Eye tracking studies therefore are performed to measure the impact of design changes to the drivers' visual attention. Cognitive models can complement these studies specifically in an early design phase as they do not require functional HMI prototypes to measure visual attention but instead generate valid predictions by simulating human visual attention based on psychological and physiological plausible models. We present a software tool that can efficiently capture operator domain knowledge, simulate human visual attention, and generate valid visual attention predictions. In an experiment we collected with the software tool knowledge from 20 car drivers in parallel session. Their aggregated attention prediction was high ($R=0.719$) and better than the average prediction of an individual HF expert (of a group of 8) compared to the drivers' monitoring behavior that we measured using an eye tracking device in a car simulator.